

tolerance limits for various ions are given in Table 1. The alkali and alkaline earth metals do

metals of similar compositions of the synthetic mixtures.

TABLE 1—EFFECTS OF DIVERSE IONS

Ion added	Amount of gold(III) taken,		Ion added	Tolerance limit ^a	
				(μg/ml)	
	FPH	PMH		FPH	PMH
Flouride	2000	1200	Rhodium(III)	16	14
Chloride	6000	5600	Osmium(VIII)	2	3
Bromide	13000	12000	Platinum(IV)	6	8
Iodide	1	0.9	Copper(II)	330	280
Nitrate	5000	7500	Nickel(II)	290	320
Sulphate	8000	16000	Cobalt(II)	170	200
Phosphate	18000	18000	Silver, I	190	8
Thiosulphate	0.5	0.4	Iron(III)	0.5	0.4
Acetate	6000	4500	Uranium(VI)	1130	1130
Citrate	6000	5000	Zinc(II)	1400	1500
Tartrate	5800	3500	Magnesium(II)	1500	1400
EDTA	2	2	Lead(II)	400	700
Palladium(II)	0.5	0.4	Arsenic(III)	70	50
Ruthenium(III)	1.5	3	Aluminium(III)	1300	1400
Iridium(III)	14	15	Molybdenum(III)	1900	1950

a=amount causing an error of less than 2%.

not interfere. The complexes formed by Pd and Pt can be removed by extraction with chloroform. The interference due to Ag(I) can be eliminated by precipitating Ag as silver chloride by adding sodium chloride.

The sensitivity of the proposed methods is more than that of 2-hydroxyl methyl-6-(5-hydroxy-2-hydroxy-methyl-pyran-4-on-6-yl)-pyrano [3,2, -b] pyran-4-8-dione (66 ng/cm²)⁴, methyl green (16 ng/cm²)⁵, hydrobromic acid (40 ng/cm²)⁶, 5-(p-ethoxy anilino)-5,6-dihydrouacil (50 ng/cm²)⁷, isonicotinic acid hydrazide (51 ng/cm²)⁸, thiocaprolactametraiodioaurate(III) (53.3 ng/cm²)⁹ and 4-(2-pyridyl-azo)-resorcinol (51 ng/cm²)¹⁰. The sensitivity of the present methods is less than that of (4-dimethylaminophenyl)(4-benzylmethylaminophenyl) anti-pyryl carbinol (3.3 ng/cm²)¹¹, pyronine G (2.03 ng/cm²)¹² and p-dimethylaminobenzylidenerhodanine (6.8 ng/cm²)¹³.

The recommended procedure was tested in mixture of synthetic solutions prepared in HCl medium (Table 2). The results indicate that the procedure described in the paper can be adopted in the analysis of Au in dental alloy or an alloy of noble

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF GOLD IN SYNTHETIC MIXTURES CORRESPONDING TO NOBLE-METAL DENTAL ALLOY USING FPH AND PMH

Au taken ppm	Ag ppm	Cu ppm	Pt ppm	Pd ppm	Zn ppm	Au found ppm
2.00	0.20	0.150	0.050	0.050	0.050	1.99
3.00	0.30	0.225	0.075	0.075	0.075	3.06
4.00	0.40	0.300	0.100	0.100	0.100	4.00
6.00	0.60	0.450	0.150	0.150	0.150	5.98
8.00	0.80	0.600	0.200	0.200	0.200	8.00

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Preparation, Magnetic Measurements and Spectral Studies on Copper(II) Complexes of Tridentate Schiff Bases

M. N. PATEL*, M. M. PATEL and C. B. PATEL

Department of Chemistry, Sardar Patel University, Vallabh Vidyanagar-388 120, Gujarat

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THERE have been numerous studies on metal chelates with ligands containing ONO donors, for instance Schiff bases^{1,2}. Previously we have reported³ the preparation and characterization of the transition metal ion complexes of the bidentate Schiff bases. Of interest in Schiff base complexes we report here copper(II) complexes of tridentate dibasic ONO donor Schiff bases derived from o-aminophenol and 3-chloro-, 4-chloro-, 4-methyl- and 5-methyl-2-hydroxyacetophenone.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COPPER(II) COMPLEXES

Compound*	Formula	Colour	Calculated(%)			Found(%)		
			Cu	C	N	Cu	C	N
1. Cu(OHA-AP)	CuC ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₃ N	Green	22.0	58.22	4.8	21.5	58.5	4.8
2. Cu(4MeOHA-AP)	CuC ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₄ N	Pale Green	20.99	59.5	4.6	20.4	59.0	4.5
3. Cu(5MeOHA-AP)	CuC ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₄ N	Green	20.99	59.5	4.6	20.6	59.5	4.5
4. Cu(3ClOHA-AP)	CuC ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₃ NCl	Pale Green	19.66	52.01	4.33	19.5	51.5	4.5
5. Cu(4ClOHA-AP)	CuC ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₃ NCl	Pale Green	19.66	52.01	4.33	19.8	52.0	4.5

*OHA=O-hydroxyacetophenone,
 AP=O-aminophenol,
 4MeOHA=4-methyl-o-hydroxyacetophenone,
 5MeOHA=5-methyl-o-hydroxyacetophenone,
 3ClOHA=3-Chloro-o-hydroxyacetophenone,
 4ClOHA=4-Chloro-o-hydroxyacetophenone.

Materials and Methods :

2-Hydroxy-3-chloroacetophenone, 2-hydroxy-4-chloroacetophenone, 2-hydroxy-4-methylacetophenone and 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone were prepared in the laboratory⁴.

Preparation of the Complexes :

The complexes were prepared by the following common method. The reaction mixture consisting of o-aminophenol and hydroxyketone with copper acetate monohydrate in appropriate amounts in absolute ethyl alcohol was refluxed about two hours. The precipitate formed was filtered, washed with ethyl alcohol and dried over calcium chloride in a desiccator.

The infrared and reflectance spectra, magnetic measurements and analysis were done as reported earlier⁵.

Results and Discussion

The results of analysis and physical properties are given in Table 1. The data show 1:1 stoichiometry which indicates that Schiff bases act as tridentate dibasic ligands.

Selected IR spectral bands, magnetic data and reflectance spectra are given in the Table 2.

TABLE 2—MAGNETIC MOMENTS, INFRARED AND REFLECTANCE SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	IR frequencies (cm ⁻¹)	Reflectance spectra
Cu(OHA-AP)	1.50	1310, 1550, 1600	700 br
Cu(4MeOHA-AP)	1.54	1290, 1550, 1605	700 br
Cu(5MeOHA-AP)	1.58	1290, 1550, 1605	700 br
Cu(3ClOHA-AP)	1.52	1290, 1550, 1605	700 br
Cu(4ClOHA-AP)	1.50	1290, 1550, 1605	700 br

The complexes behave as non-electrolytes in DMF as revealed by their molar conductances

which fall in the range 0-1 mho cm² mole⁻¹. The electronic spectra of all the complexes show a broad absorption around 700 nm indicating a square or distorted configuration⁶⁻⁷. The C=N stretching vibrations appear in the region 1600 and the enolic C—O appears in the region 1300 cm⁻¹. This suggests that the ligand is coordinated through oxygen and nitrogen of CO and C=N groups respectively. Similar observations have also been made by Biradar *et al.*⁸. The band at 1550 cm⁻¹ is taken as an unambiguous criterion for the formation of a phenolic oxygen-bridging between the two adjacent copper atoms⁹. The disappearance of the stretching of the phenolic OH, observed around 3300 cm⁻¹ in case of o-hydroxyketones, clearly indicates the loss of phenolic proton on coordination and formation of a new bond between metal and oxygen⁹.

The room temperature magnetic moments of the complexes are markedly less than the spin-only value of 1.73 B.M. expected for one unpaired electron. Recently¹⁰ the low value (1.6 B.M.) at room temperature for the copper complex of Schiff base derived from salicylal-4-amino antipyrine was assigned to a dimeric structure. In conclusion, these chelates can attain a four-coordinate planar structure presumably by the dimerization of two tridentate Cu(II) units through an oxygen bridge.

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Use of Ortho-substituted Benzalidine-thiosemicarbazone as Analytical Reagent— Gravimetric Determination of Ni(II)

Y. THAKUR*, J. THAKUR and A. K. SINGH

Department of Chemistry, L. S. College, Muzaffarpur,
Bihar University, Muzaffarpur

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accepted 19 November 1979

DIMETHYLGlyOXIME has been used as an analytical reagent for gravimetric analysis of nickel and palladium. The difficulty arises in the determination of nickel in the presence of large amounts of cobalt ion. Also use of excess ammonia causes the dissolution of nickel dimethylglyoxime complex, but the precipitation of Ni(II) with *o*-nitrobenzalidinetiosemicarbazone and *o*-chlorobenzalidinetiosemicarbazone is complete at pH = 8-9. Palladium(II) does not interfere while the precipitation of Co(II), Cu(II) and Fe(III) are prevented by using suitable masking agents.

Experimental

All reagents used were of A. R. grade stock solutions of nickel (1%) was prepared by dissolving nickel sulphate in double distilled water and 1% ethanol solution of the ligands was employed.

Preparation of the Ligands :—(a) *O*-nitrobenzalidinetiosemicarbazone :—*O*-nitrobenzaldehyde was prepared as described in the literature¹.

(b) *O*-chlorobenzalidinetiosemicarbazone :—It was prepared by dissolving *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde in ethanol and treating it with thiosemicarbazide dissolved in concentrated hydrochloric acid. The ligand was obtained as a pale yellow precipitate. The precipitate was recrystallised from ethanol and dried (m.p. 217°).

Determination of Nickel :—A solution containing known amount of nickel(II) was diluted to 100 ml

* Present address :—Head of the Department of Chemistry, Mithila University, Darbhanga.

and heated to 50-60°. The hot solution was then treated with an ethanol solution of the ligand. The pH was adjusted to 8-9 with dilute ammonia. A brown precipitate (red precipitate in the case of *o*-chlorobenzalidinetiosemicarbazone) was obtained. The whole mass was digested on steam-bath for about half an hour, filtered through a sintered glass crucible (G-4) and washed with hot water and ethanol. The precipitate was dried in an air-oven at 120-130° to constant weight, weighed as Ni(C₈H₇N₄O₂S)₂ and Ni(C₈H₇N₄SCl)₂ respectively in the case of *o*-nitrobenzalidinetiosemicarbazone and *o*-chlorobenzalidinetiosemicarbazone. The complexes are soluble in acetone but insoluble in ethanol and methanol. The results of some of the estimations are tabulated below :—

TABLE 1—GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF Ni(II) AT pH=8-9 : (a) *o*-NITRO-(b) *o*-CHLOROBENZALIDINETHIOSEMICARBAZONE

No.	Ni(II) taken (mg)	Ni(II) complex (mg)		Ni(II) found (mg)		% error	
		(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)
1.	10	86.00	83.90	10.01	10.01	+0.10	+0.10
2.	20	172.10	168.00	20.04	20.03	+0.20	+0.15
3.	30	257.10	252.00	30.05	30.04	+0.16	+0.13

Pd(II) is precipitated with these reagents at pH=2-3 hence it can be separated from nickel at this pH range. Cu(II) is precipitated as blackish brown ppt. at pH=6-8 hence it interferes. The interference can be avoided by the addition of potassium tartarate. Co(II) is not precipitated by the reagents. Fe(III) is also prevented to precipitate by using potassium tartarate as masking agent. Thus Ni(II) (20 mg) can be determined in the presence of 10mg of Cu(II) or Fe(III), the maximum error being 1%.

Structure of the Chelates :—Ortho-substituted benzalidine-thiosemicarbazones behave as bidentate ligands in neutral, ammoniacal and acid media. The chemical analysis of the complexes indicate that they have the chemical formula(I). Ni(C₈H₇N₄O₂S)₂ (Found : C-38%, H-2.60%, N-22%, Ni-11.60%, Calculated : C-38.04%, H-2.78%, N-22.20%, Ni-11.63%). (II) Ni(C₈H₇N₄SCl)₂ (Found : C-39.70%, H-2.80%, N-17.20%, Ni-12.10%, Calculated : C-39.60%, H-2.90%, H-2.90%, N-17.36%, Ni-12.14%).

The complexes are diamagnetic. Their acetone solns. show maximum absorption band at about 15000 cm⁻¹. The magnetic behaviour and electronic spectra² suggest for square planar structure of the complexes. The I.R. spectra of the complexes have been recorded to determine the nature of bonding in the complexes. The presence of a sharp band at about 5050 cm⁻¹ both in the ligands